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For several decades now, not only the topic of racism but also the topic of gender justice has been gaining more and more space in the "West". This applies in the scientific field as well as in the political public. It permeates everyday life even more. In the virtual world of media, especially in advertising, the design of idols and their presentation play a central role. Such "idols" are always endowed with attributes that emphasize their affiliation to genders particularly simply and clearly.

For me, all of these are indications of the increasing loss of the individual in an ever increasing number of people. The questions: Who am I ?, - Do I mean something? How do I measure myself? - lead to what one describes as a competition. This competition, the desire to rise above others is a fundamental need of every individual. This is not only evident in the animal kingdom, the magnificent feathers of a male peacock are an example of this. It is astonishing that "western" women, in order to "attract attention", use the very fashion tools that they complain of elsewhere as "sexist".

Looking back, there is a fundamental difference between the basic philosophical positions of Orient and Occident. It concerns the self-image of the individual, regardless of whether female or male. Very simply, it consists of the following:

The westerner believes: I will because I am. The exact opposite runs through the Far Eastern schools of thought: I am because I am. In other words: For the Orient, the way is the goal, as long as this Orient was not influenced by Western ideas. That is changing.

If one abstracts from the individual case, there are two contradicting views of female and male as between the Orient and the Occident. Only female beings produce "fruits". You could say they are because they are made with their fruits. In mammals, especially in humans, the male beings generally ensure another, equally important condition of reproduction so that "the offspring", especially not their own, actually have a future. They become fathers and later patriarchs because they are. You can defend yourself and your family.

Another thought:

Mentally, a human child is only fully developed at around 3 years old. In contrast to other mammals of this age, it is far from being able to survive independently. In order to become culturally viable, a development phase is required that extends far beyond biological reproductive capacity. In these special development phases, boys and girls, men and women, fathers and mothers, grandfathers and grandmothers each play a very different role. Their mutual relationship changes fundamentally. I certainly do not need to explain this further.

It becomes visible from such a cross-generational perspective, which, unlike the gender "science", is not a snapshot: the function of male and female changes in the transmission of "life" over longer periods of time. Changing types and forms of division of labor between "men" and "women" are required in this dynamic process.

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The change from hunting and collecting societies to agricultural societies, in particular the development of advanced cultures, especially the process of mechanization, industrialization and above all mass urbanization has had a decisive influence on this division of roles more than ever - and this is almost becoming completely overlooked: A statistically shaped description of "male beings" between 1 year and almost 100 years old can no more be understood by "man" than it is by the equivalent of "woman".

There was not the legendary Queen of Sheba, the pharaoh Hatshepsut, later Cleopatra, the Caesar and then Marc Anton, finally Queen Elizabeth I (1558), who had Maria Stuart executed, Empress Maria Theresa (1740), Catherine the Great (1762), Queen Victoria (1837)?

In the modern sense, women naturally rule over men: Margaret Thatcher levered out the male-dominated unions with the help of the military and waged the Falklands War. Christine Lagarde, Ursula von der Leyen and Angela Merkel are currently forming a power cartel. They form a veritable triumvirate, similar to that triumvirate, the male conspiracy with which Pompeius, Crassus and Caesar once fundamentally changed the political structures of ancient Rome and formed an empire out of a kind of democracy.

At that time the Consul Bibulus opposed this in vain. Today Emmanuel Macron seems to be doing the same in Europe.

So what is the struggle for the equality of "women" other than one of those narratives with which people of both sexes can be brought together to form a kind of movement, a sect, and which "activists" some time later give power, influence and money.

One final remark. What used to be called patriarchy has now mutated into the phenomenon of a "caring" state. In social communities not only today, but always women also determine what their "protégés" are allowed to do and what not. There were queens, empresses and meanwhile presidents and Chancellors. To accuse this person of dominance today would then, in the understanding of gender movements, "to revolt against the constitution." The modern welfare state has no gender, it has become a blind juggernaut who claims the children for themselves, who prescribes how they are brought up and who includes them in "generational contracts" without even asking them about them.